

LandSense

A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

Deliverable D6.3

Ecosystem building and service incubator activities I

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Short Description:
This deliverable provides insights into the consortium activities with respect to ecosystem building. Activities undertaken, and stakeholders engaged in the first half of the project are elaborated in detail, with attention given to first LandSense Innovation Challenge organized as the incubator event for ecosystem and services building. The deliverable also includes a brief illustration of the value chain, its stakeholders and LandSense positioning within the ecosystem.
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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	7
1 Introduction.....	8
2 Scope and Objectives.....	9
3 LandSense Ecosystem Building Activities	10
3.1 Ecosystem Incubator Events	10
3.1.1 LandSense Challenge Dissemination	18
3.1.2 LandSense Challenge Feedback.....	21
3.2 Notable LandSense Activities aimed at Ecosystem Building.....	21
3.2.1 EC Cluster Workshop – Brussels, Belgium	22
3.2.2 LandSense at WorldCover 2017 – Frascati, Italy	22
3.2.3 LandSense at the GEO-CRADLE Regional Workshop – Bucharest, Romania	23
3.2.4 LandSense at the 11 th European GEO Workshop – Helsinki, Finland	23
3.2.5 Defining the Urban Landscape Dynamics Pilot – Toulouse, France	24
3.2.6 LandSense meets Deutsches Forschungsnetz – Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (DFN-AAI) – Berlin, Germany	24
3.2.7 LandSense at Open Science 2017 – Frascati, Italy	25
3.2.8 The 6 th ECN Crowdfunding Convention – Vilnius, Lithuania.....	25
3.2.9 VUA presents LandSense to the local Dutch government officials – Amsterdam, Netherlands.....	26
3.2.10 LandSense at the 106 th Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) Technical Committee meeting – Orleans, France.....	26
3.2.11 LandSense integrates Geospatial User Feedback System – Barcelona, Spain.....	26
3.2.12 LandSense at 3 rd ECN CrowdCamp – Bologna, Italy.....	27
3.3 Common Dissemination Booster (CDB) and collaboration with other H2020 Citizen Observatories ...	27
4 The illustration of the value chain	28
5 Future Activities.....	29
6 Conclusions.....	30
Annex.....	31
First LandSense Innovation Challenge Call	31
First LandSense Innovation Challenge Application Form	35
First LandSense Innovation Challenge Proposal Template.....	36
First LandSense Innovation Challenge Agenda	38
First LandSense Challenge Survey.....	39

List of Figures

Figure 1 Insights from the LandSense Innovation Challenge	11
Figure 2 Insights from Monitoring Water Levels from Space presentation	12
Figure 3 Insights from Open Change Detection Map Presentation	13
Figure 4 Insights from Bioenergy potentials from agricultural residues Presentation	14
Figure 5 Insights from Land Surface Temperature Monitoring Using Sentinel 3 Satellite Imagery for Habitat Loss Prevention in Protected Areas Presentation	15
Figure 6 Insights from Agricultural Satellite Monitoring Presentation	16
Figure 7 Insights from Bird's AI - Automated Monitoring of Land Use and Land Cover Presentation.....	17
Figure 8 Team Bird's AI wins the First LandSense Innovation Challenge	18
Figure 9 LandSense Website statistics (Sept, 2016- May,2017)	19
Figure 10 Earth Observation actors sharing news about LandSense Innovation Challenge	19
Figure 11 Call for LandSense Challenge Innovation at HackEvents and HackFest	20
Figure 12 L andSense Innovation Challenge being promoted through LandSense channels	20
Figure 13 LandSense Ecosystem Building Survey Findings.....	21
Figure 14 The Earth Observation Market	28

List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence	IT	Information Technologies
CDB	Common Dissemination Booster	JRC	Joint Research Centre
CS	Citizen Science	KBA	Key Biodiversity Areas
CSA	Community Supported Agriculture	LEP	LandSense Engagement Platform
DFN-	Deutsches Forschungsnetz –	LULC	Land Use and Land Cover
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure		
DITO	Doing it together science	NGO	Non-Government Organization
EC	European Commission	NMAs	National Meteorological Administration
ECN	European Crowdfunding Network	NOA	National Observatory of Athens
EEN	Enterprise Europe Network	OCDM	Open Change Detection Map
EO	Earth Observation	OGC	The Open Geospatial Consortium
EODC	Earth Observation Data Centre	OSM	OpenStreetMap
EOS	Earth Observation Systems	Q&A	Questions and Answers
ESCA	European Citizen Science Association	QA	Quality Assurance
EU	European Union	R&D	Research and Development
GEOSS	Global Earth Observations System of Systems	RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
GIS	Geographic Information System	SME	Small and Medium size Enterprises
GSA	European Global Satellite Agency	VC	Venture Capital
GUF	Geospatial User Feedback	VGI	Volunteered Geographic Information
IBAs	Important Bird and Biodiversity Areas	INOE	The National Institute of R&D for Optoelectronics

Executive Summary

LandSense is one of four Horizon 2020 projects funded under the SC5-17-2015 - Demonstrating the concept of 'Citizen Observatories' call. The project started on 1st of September 2016 and aims to build a far-reaching citizen observatory for Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) monitoring that will also function as a technology innovation marketplace. Led by the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA) 18 partners from 9 European countries have teamed up to mobilize and deliver an observatory and innovation marketplace that combines the powers of Citizen Science (CS) and Earth Observation (EO) for LULC monitoring.

D6.3 Ecosystem building and services incubator I outlines the activities undertaken in the first half of the project with the goal of disseminating innovative elements within the LandSense project, facilitating collaboration, engaging identified stakeholders to understand and to use the LandSense results for their own interests/organization and ultimately providing feedback for more effective exploitation potential of the project results. The deliverable will also include a brief illustration of the value chain and its stakeholders.

Throughout the project consortium partners carried out a number of ecosystem building activities, actions and events, according to the time plan. Printable informational dissemination material was distributed at each of the mentioned events. These actions were in compliance with the overall dissemination strategy.

This deliverable will be updated in the D6.8 Ecosystem building and services incubator II which is due on Month 48 of the project.

1 Introduction

LandSense is an EU-funded project dedicated towards building an innovative citizen observatory in the field of LULC, by collecting data both actively (through citizens) and passively (from authoritative, open access, and other citizen-based initiatives) and integrating it into an open platform that provides valuable quality-assured in-situ data for SMEs, larger businesses, government agencies, NGOs and researchers to use. A key component of the LandSense Citizen Observatory is the LandSense engagement platform (D3.3) that facilitates innovative environmental monitoring by connecting communities, LandSense core services, data resources and demonstration cases. To this end, the project aims to uncover the collective potential of CS and EO to improve our environmental knowledge base, which includes the production of accurate information on land use, land cover (LULC) and changes to the landscape over time.

LandSense services are designed to contribute to LULC monitoring within three major themes, urban landscape dynamics, agricultural land use, and forestry and habitat. For example, innovative tools provide farmers with information on vegetation health status from remotely sensed EO data as an incentive to share data on crops grown, crop phenological information (e.g. emergence and flowering), management information (e.g. dates of planting and harvest as well as nutrient use and application), occurrence of pests and diseases and impact of extreme weather.

This deliverable signifies the activities undertaken with the respect to LandSense ecosystem building. Ecosystem building activities are crucial not only for the development of project's outputs, but also for the positioning of the project within the EO value chain, ultimately strengthening post-project exploitation opportunities. The deliverable will be updated in M48 in D6.8 Ecosystem building and service incubator activities II.

In particular, the report is structured into 5 distinct sections as follows:

- **Section 1** provides introductory information with respect to the LandSense project and the context in which the current report has been elaborated.
- **Section 2** outlines the scope, objectives and the importance of ecosystem building
- **Section 3** presents LandSense partners corresponding activities, engagement and achievements in respect to ecosystem building
- **Section 4** illustrates the EO value chain from a LandSense perspective
- **Section 5** sheds light on the upcoming ecosystem building activities anticipated for the project

2 Scope and Objectives

The overarching objective of this deliverable is to summarize the LandSense consortium's activities and achievements towards creating a valuable ecosystem of stakeholders who support further development of the project within the broad Earth Observation ecosystem in Europe.

More specifically, the objectives of LandSense ecosystem building include the following:

- To better understand the different ways EO stakeholders are currently engaged in LULC activities within the EO Ecosystem as well as the extent of their engagement.
- To capture the geographical scope of the online collaborations for innovation within LandSense domains and evaluate the willingness of relevant stakeholders to establish new or enhance their existing online collaborations for innovation
- To involve relevant EO stakeholders in the LandSense ecosystem with the goal of expanding its userbase; involve as many active players in iterative lean development process and thus further develop LandSense services; bring on new partners who will attach their own services and products to the LandSense offerings; to engage stakeholders through open innovation to build on LandSense offerings
- To identify the main barriers that appear to be preventing LandSense from expanding its innovation activities as well as key success factors that may facilitate its adoption to their business and innovation processes.
- To gain insights into the perceived knowledge, skills, tools and/or support that stakeholders require in order to successfully capitalize on LandSense innovation.

The scope of the LandSense ecosystem building is to include SMEs from across the EO value chain and its supporting industries (i.e. from end-users including research organizations, technology firms, enterprises, data providers/data seekers, public bodies, to citizens as a whole.) as well as representatives of innovation intermediaries and SME support networks across Europe. Interconnections and interdependencies created through LandSense incubator activities provide relevant organizations with knowledge of how to use LandSense outcomes for their own interests.

3 LandSense Ecosystem Building Activities

3.1 Ecosystem Incubator Events

Two Ecosystem incubator events / Challenges were planned and aimed at engaging citizen science community and other EO actors with LandSense project and platform.

The [First LandSense Challenge](#) was designed to target EO involved individuals, web-entrepreneurs, start-ups and SMEs coming from all participating Horizon 2020 countries (See Annex for call documents). The Challenge invited participants to present innovative IT ideas addressing one of the three LandSense domains: Urban Landscape Dynamics, Agricultural Land Use, and Forest & Habitat Monitoring. The challenge focused on using data streams coming from the LandSense Citizen Observatory, the Sentinel Hub Service or other relevant EO data sources to design novel LULC solutions for a range of applications within the selected domains.

The First LandSense Innovation Challenge, based on a Hackathon concept, supported knowledge sharing through a one-day event where participants present and share their technical capabilities, innovation and creativity.

The objectives of the First LandSense Innovation Challenge are to:

- Promote the best pitch presentations that could have a clear business impact
- Create awareness about the LandSense project objectives and outcomes
- Foster the community spirit within the LandSense Citizen Observatory

Each of the finalists received:

- A travel voucher in the amount of 250 EUR per team for attending the event in Geneva
- One ticket per team at a discounted rate to attend the Second International ECSA Conference 2018 (Cost: 50 EUR)
- Business coaching and mentorship services at the challenge
- Matchmaking and networking opportunities with leading experts in EO and citizen science
- Promotional services by LandSense
- Presentation about the LandSense Engagement Platform at the Conference in Geneva

The team with the best pitch in Geneva will receive:

- A grand prize of 1,500 EUR (in the form of a check presented at the event)
- A 1-year subscription to Sentinel Hub Enterprise, worth 5,000 EUR, provided by SINERGISE
- Online business coaching and mentorship services provided by the InoSens team

Six LandSense Challenge finalists were invited, upon the completion of the open call that lasted for two and a half months, to pitch their ideas at the [Second International ECSA Conference 2018](#) on 3 June 2018 in Geneva, Switzerland. Additional information about the dissemination of the Challenge open call can be found in the subsequent section.

Competition at the First LandSense Innovation Challenge was high, as six teams from four European countries presented a variety of novel and ground-breaking ideas for: Monitoring Water levels, Optimizing Bioenergy Potentials, Agricultural Satellite Monitoring, Land Surface Temperature Monitoring, Automated Monitoring of Land Use and Land Cover, and Change Detection Mapping.

During the Challenge the participants were active in boot camp style sessions led by LandSense partners. Session topics included introductory session on LandSense Engagement Platform, Sentinel Hub Services, Citizen Science (CS) and idea pitching skills, thereby encouraging contributions to the EO, CS and investor communities, etc. The event was an ideal opportunity for all the participants and finalists to network and exchange ideas with scientists, practitioners and other key stakeholders in order to boost citizen science in the environmental monitoring context. Additionally, participants also seized the opportunity improve their pitches and sought further coaching from the LandSense partners. The LandSense jury members were composed of LandSense consortium partners INOSENS, SINERGISE, IIASA, GeoVille and the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA), and an expert advisory board member from University College London.

Evaluation of the idea pitches was very demanding as each team were allotted 5 minutes for their pitch with 5 minutes for Q&A. The idea was to give the participants the sense of Venture Capital evaluation process and prepare them for the market. After each unique pitch, the LandSense jury members made sure their line of questioning was thorough and that it pushed the participants to the limits (See Annex for evaluation criteria). The LandSense jury still found it very difficult to distinguish one idea that stood above all the rest as each idea possessed its own value, market potential and was very relevant to the domain. Summaries of the various pitches are provided below.

Figure 1 Insights from the LandSense Innovation Challenge

Finalists Pitch Summaries:

Organization: BlueDot Observatory (Slovenia)
Team: Anze Zupanc
Idea Name: Monitoring Water Levels from Space
LandSense domain: Forest & Habitat Monitoring.

Pitch Summary:

Monitoring Water Levels from Space is an EO-based solution that will provide both global historical and current data on water resources condition. As this data will be publicly available, not only water authorities but also interested citizens will better understand the state of their local and global environment.

BlueDot Water Observatory
 Observing the water levels of water bodies all over the globe from space.

Figure 2 Insights from Monitoring Water Levels from Space presentation

Organization: OpenChangeDetectionMap (Spain)

Team: Rohini Swaminathan and Marcos Moreu

Idea Name: Open Change Detection Map

LandSense domain: Urban Landscape Dynamics, Agricultural Land Use, and Forest & Habitat Monitoring.

Pitch Summary:

OpenChangeDetectionMap (OCDM) is an open collaborative project to map changes on earth using Geospatial Information Technologies and Big Data. Any change, anywhere, by anyone, for everyone. OCDM project’s goal is to democratize the access to earth observation-derived information to ensure that the impacts of human activities are monitored, evidence-based decisions are made and are sustainable and fair development becomes a reality for all.

What is OCDM?

An **open collaborative project** to map changes on earth’s surface, detected using **Geospatial Information Technologies** and **Big Data**. **Any change, anywhere, by anyone, for everyone.**

Goal

Democratize the access to **earth observation-derived information** to ensure that the impacts of human activities are monitored, evidence based decisions are made and **sustainable** and **fair development** becomes a reality for all

Figure 3 Insights from Open Change Detection Map Presentation

Organization: Geodetic Institute of Slovenia (Slovenia)
Team: Alen Mangafic
Idea Name: Bioenergy potentials from agricultural residues
LandSense domain: Agricultural Land Use

Pitch Summary:

This pitch proposes a methodology for the estimation of bioenergy potential from crop residues and to connect local farmers and landscape companies in cooperatives, which can produce their own energy on a local scale. The network-based analysis would define possible optimal locations for biomass facilities. The time-series analysis of middle-season crop phenology would simulate the energy potential that the facilities can expect at the end of the season.

Figure 4 Insights from Bioenergy potentials from agricultural residues Presentation

University of Ljubljana

Organization: University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)

Team: Monja Šebela and Matic Vehovac

Idea Name: Land Surface Temperature Monitoring Using Sentinel 3 Satellite Imagery for Habitat Loss Prevention in Protected Areas

LandSense domain: Urban Landscape Dynamics, Agricultural Land Use, and Forest & Habitat Monitoring.

Pitch Summary:

The idea is to create an application that would monitor the land surface temperature of designated protected areas. It would collect both past and present data of land surface temperature and monitor habitat stress levels that are based on their tolerance range. The application would display relevant data and visualise trends. As soon as temperature would reach a dangerous level, the application would issue a warning. The data that the application would display would be much more precise than currently available data. The process of data acquisition would be faster and cheaper than current methods of temperature measurement, which rely on expensive climatological stations and spatial interpolation in areas where these stations do not exist.

Figure 5 Insights from Land Surface Temperature Monitoring Using Sentinel 3 Satellite Imagery for Habitat Loss Prevention in Protected Areas Presentation

Team: Athanasios-Emmanouil Mourampetzis and Asimakis Fylaktos (Greece)

Idea Name: Agricultural Satellite Monitoring

LandSense domain: Agricultural Land Use

Pitch Summary:

The vision is to create an application that will help farmers profit from every acre. Since food is the primary invest of humankind, our priority is to optimize farming. The project’s target is to provide a mobile application with a simple user-interface. The application’s features will be available with a monthly / yearly subscription. The user will be able to mark and monitor his land via remote sensing data which automatically will provide them with enough information for more viable agricultural techniques. We invest on the next generation of farmers, those who will depend on high precision farming. For the first time, farmers can combine remote sensing tools and their personal log for precise farming of their land, with minimum expenses and a company that interacts directly with them.

THANK YOU

IDEA & VISION

- The gap can be managed with the use of precise agricultural techniques.
- Our vision is to create a mobile application that will provide farmers with all data required to maximize their land's productivity.
- Weather forecast, risk for flood/drought, diseases or fire, and evapotranspiration are the factors for precision farming.
- Sentinel 1, Sentinel 2, Sentinel 3, and Proba V give these data.

BUSINESS MODEL

- The app is going to be created inside the team
- Recruiting new members (Programmer & marketing specialist).
- Minimizing our advertisement expenses.
- Creating a network of third-party associates / "ambassadors".

THE APPLICATION

- The raw data will be processed via a GIS based SQL server that will automatically run scripts between raster and vector layers combining them into a final map that will be uploaded to the web server and presented to the user.
- The user will mark his land and regularly receive data (warnings, charts, suggestions) regarding his marked area. All of the above will be saved into the FARMER'S LOG.

Expense Report

FARMER'S LOG app PROMOTION

ASM team +

Figure 6 Insights from Agricultural Satellite Monitoring Presentation

Organization: Bird's AI (The Netherlands)

Team: Rosalie and Daniel van der Maas

Idea Name: Automated Monitoring of Land Use and Land Cover

LandSense domain: Urban Landscape Dynamics, Agricultural Land Use, and Forest & Habitat Monitoring.

Pitch Summary:

Bird's AI positions itself in the remote sensing market as a company that discloses low cost satellite data, analysis, and interpretation, to government agencies, international organizations, NGOs, companies and researchers who have a need for better and cheaper land use and land cover monitoring, by making use of automated and standardized Artificially Intelligent models within a scalable data infrastructure as opposed to costly, labour intensive, case-by-case monitoring and measuring methods.

Scalable
Low cost

Model: Land usage
 Satellite: Sentinel 2
 Latitude: 52.329146895129 to 58.3536147076094
 Longitude: 5.54833884375001 to 16.38371883750004
 Date: dd-mm-yy
 Max days before given date:
 Month: From January to December
 Cloud coverage: Less than %
 Daylight only:
 Name for this request:
 E-mail:
 Make request

Figure 7 Insights from Bird's AI - Automated Monitoring of Land Use and Land Cover Presentation

Ultimately it came to a decision that a Dutch team consisting of Rosalie van der Maas and Daniel van der Maas with the idea "Bird's AI – Automated Monitoring of Land Use and Land Cover" takes the first prize at the first LandSense Innovation Challenge.

Figure 8 Team Bird's AI wins the First LandSense Innovation Challenge

The winning team received a 1 year subscription to Sentinel Hub Enterprise, worth 5,000 EUR, provided by SINERGISE, online business coaching and mentorship services provided by INOSENS and a grand prize of 1,500 EUR. LandSense is will continue collaborating with Bird’s AI in the upcoming months!

3.1.1 LandSense Challenge Dissemination

The First LandSense Innovation Challenge open call lasted from 1st of February until April 13th. During this time, INOSENS led the dissemination activities, with LandSense partners also sharing the prepared information through their own online channels.

INOSENS promoted the open call through online social networks Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, actively engaging Earth Observation, GIS, environmental and remote sensing influencers to further share the posts. In addition, 100+ EEN contact points, 100+ academia and partner contacts, and the EO start-up community were engaged through IONSENSE direct contacts. Horizon2020 project and EU accelerator KATANA was engaged for further disseminating the news about the Challenge with its SMEs from the agricultural sector. Collaboration with the organisers of CAPIGI hackathon was established, namely FarmHackNL, WNF-NL and CAPIGI, for further disseminating the news about LandSense Challenge and future events among our respective participants.

During the dissemination of the LandSense Challenge, we recorded 2,100 visits to the Challenge [webpage](#), which drastically increased LandSense website traction and visibility, as can be seen in figure below.

Figure 9 LandSense Website statistics (Sept, 2016- May, 2017)

Figure 10 Earth Observation actors sharing news about LandSense Innovation Challenge

Figure 11 Call for LandSense Challenge Innovation at HackEvents and HackFest

Figure 12 LandSense Innovation Challenge being promoted through LandSense channels

3.1.2 LandSense Challenge Feedback

To acquire feedback from the finalists a short survey (See Annex) was distributed. The findings indicate that the participants considered the event to be very well organized and informative, with the event having medium-to-high networking opportunities. Moreover, the participants indicated notable interest in future LandSense Events and Challenges, which further indicates that incubator events such as this one are an excellent way for LandSense to engage with its stakeholders and potential users of its services.

Figure 13 LandSense Ecosystem Building Survey Findings

Additional Testimonials

- “I am really hoping that the near future events are going to be as interesting as this one with a lot more participants” – **Alen Mangafić**
- “LS Challenge was very well executed, with all aspects prepared professionally” **Matic Vehovec**
- “It would be nice if there were more people expressing their needs. What are people looking for in your innovation market place?” **Anze Zupanc**

3.2 Notable LandSense Activities aimed at Ecosystem Building

This section summarizes a few notable LandSense activities where LandSense partners had an opportunity to meet with representatives of influential Earth Observation networks, policy makers, researchers, SMEs, public and other relevant stakeholders through organized workshops, conferences, hackathons and meetings. Each of the following activities has contributed to building awareness of the LandSense project and expanding the project’s involvement in the EO industry. The activities have empowered the LandSense federated system to bring in partners to develop synergies, while enabling the scaling-up of existing services, knowledge bases and novel value-added LULC products. Moreover, through such collective interaction with the involved stakeholders, this ‘power of collaboration’ will lead to the fast adoption of LandSense services and ultimately strengthen the projects ecosystem for an effective post-project exploitation.

3.2.1 EC Cluster Workshop – Brussels, Belgium

24.-25.11.2016

LandSense representatives from IIASA attended the very successful EC cluster workshop in Brussels, Belgium at the end of November 2016. The LandSense team met with other H2020 citizen observatories (SCENT, GroundTruth 2.0, GROW) as well as the FP-7 pioneer projects and shared their lessons learned from the outgoing projects and discussed collaboration opportunities for the future. LandSense was very well represented at the event, with LandSense Coordinator Steffen Fritz showcasing the project, and several members of the project presenting main parts in detail, namely, the demo cases, technical parts, the LandSense federation and the engagement platform.

3.2.2 LandSense at WorldCover 2017 – Frascati, Italy

14.-16.03.2017

IIASA was presenting LandSense at the WorldCover Conference hosted by the European Space Agency in March 2017. The conference brought together Land Cover users, scientists, students as well as representatives from National, European and International Space Agencies, Value Adding Industries, Laboratories and Universities. This event proved to be great opportunity to introduce the project to the LULC community.

Link to the conference: <http://worldcover2017.esa.int>

3.2.3 LandSense at the GEO-CRADLE Regional Workshop – Bucharest, Romania

09.05.2017

Igor Milosavljevic from INOSENS represented LandSense at the regional workshop of Geo-Cradle in Bucharest on 9th of May 2017. LandSense was presented as a success story project in the Balkan Region, including a general overview of the project and how it contributes to the Earth Observation sector in the region.

The event was part of a CSA to promote advancement of the Earth Observation sector in the Balkans, North Africa and the Middle East. The event aimed at engaging the Romanian EO community and was jointly organized by the National Observatory of Athens (NOA) and the National Institute of R&D for Optoelectronics (INOE).

Link to the workshop <http://geocradle.eu/en/regional-workshop-romania/>

3.2.4 LandSense at the 11th European GEO Workshop – Helsinki, Finland

22.06.2017

LandSense representatives were participating at the 11th European Geo Workshop at Helsinki, Finland. The event brought together European stakeholders, interested in and actively contributing to the Global Earth Observations System of Systems (GEOSS). The event was an ideal forum to exchange ideas and to inform participants about work and initiatives undertaken in the context of GEOSS. LandSense coordinator Steffen Fritz and Ian McCallum from IIASA co-shared Session 15 on acceptance, quality, and integration of citizen-science data for evidence-driven environmental

governance. This session was dedicated to sharing approaches and existing algorithms for ensuring citizen-observed data quality. The session addressed, among other things, the issue of the general acceptance of citizen science data for evidence-driven environmental governance. Furthermore, success stories and lessons learned were presented from the perspective of public authorities based on citizen-science activities. In his talk, Steffen Fritz provided an overview of the acceptance, quality, and integration of citizen-science data in LandSense.

Andreas Matheus from Secure Dimension then provided an overview of the lessons learned, best practices, and challenges with respect to the harmonisation of citizen-generated data within LandSense. His talk contributed to Session 9 Citizen Observatories and Harmonisation of Citizen-Generated Data: Best practices

and challenges, which was dedicated to data harmonisation approaches to improve citizen generated data-sharing and data reuse for environmental monitoring.

Link to the workshop <https://ec.europa.eu/easme/en/european-geo-workshop-2017>

3.2.5 Defining the Urban Landscape Dynamics Pilot – Toulouse, France

19.09.2017

A dedicated stakeholder workshop was held by LandSense partner IGN-France in Toulouse in mid-July 2017. The workshop aimed at informing participants about the details of the planned campaign in the city. Furthermore, the requirements, tools, and data needed for the validation of the campaign were discussed.

Following a short introduction of the overall aim and objectives of the LandSense project, the implementation of the urban landscapes dynamic case for Toulouse was discussed. This included, among other things, an analysis of the data requirements, a presentation of the LandSense

Change Detection Service, as well as goals and strategies for the campaign. Importantly, the areas of interest for the campaign were defined in accordance with stakeholder inputs.

The meeting was well received and included 18 participants from local governments, private companies, universities, and national research institutes dealing with LULC, who have expressed interest in LandSense and were willing to participate in the campaign. A local representative from OpenStreetMap France also attended the meeting.

3.2.6 LandSense meets Deutsches Forschungsnetz – Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (DFN-AAI) – Berlin, Germany

21.09.2017

LandSense partner Andreas Matheus from Secure Dimension met with representatives from the Deutsches Forschungsnetz – Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (DFN-AAI) to explore the potential of the LandSense Engagement Platform. The meeting was hosted at the DFN-AAI office in Berlin, Germany.

The main objective of the meeting was to elaborate on the possibilities to connect the LandSense Engagement Platform to interested organisations from the German Academic Federation. This would enable participating

institutions to join LandSense using their own organisational accounts. Besides technical aspects and requirements, legal and organisational conditions for joining the DFN-AAI network were discussed. The successful meeting ended with the conclusion that there are no obstacles for LandSense to join DFN-AAI.

3.2.7 LandSense at Open Science 2017 – Frascati, Italy

25.09.2017

Matej Aleksandrov from SINERGISE gave a Lightning Talk explaining the collaborative and innovative research, undertaken with IASA that engages the public in an initiative involving ESA's Sentinel-2 satellite imagery. Matej presented a short plan on engaging citizens to delineate clouds in Sentinel-2 data in order to help build a manual high-quality database of clouds and cloud shadows. The tool is supposed to be included in the LandSense Engagement Platform and gained a lot of traction,

particularly as the tool will be configurable and users will be able to specify their own classes to be classified (e.g. land classes). The tool build on top of SINERGISE's knowledge of EO data and IASA's expertise on building high quality data from crowdsourced information.

3.2.8 The 6th ECN Crowdfunding Convention – Vilnius, Lithuania

09.11.2017

Francesca Passeri from the European Crowdfunding Network represented LandSense at the 6th ECN Crowdfunding Convention (CrowdCon) in Vilnius, Lithuania. The convention was an ideal platform for LandSense partners to meet EU and national-level policy-makers, as well as professionals and stakeholders from the European crowdfunding industry to promote and raise awareness about the LandSense project and its activities.

More info about the Exhibition: <https://www.world-efficiency.com/fr/world-efficiency/WE-Paris/>

3.2.9 VUA presents LandSense to local Dutch officials – Amsterdam, Netherlands

04.04.2018

VU University Amsterdam presented LandSense and the NL Greenspace app to the local Dutch government officials. Local government officials were engaged to provide input on what they would like to see in the app, and plans were made for collaborative launch/promotion. The app is currently being piloted in Rembrandt Park in Amsterdam.

3.2.10 LandSense at the 106th Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) Technical Committee meeting – Orleans, France

06.04.2018

Andreas Matheus (Secure Dimensions) and Christoph Perger (IIASA) represented LandSense and introduced the LandSense Engagement Platform. Discussions about engagement followed among domain experts from the OGC Citizen Science Domain Working Group and the Europe Forum. With participants from government, commercial organizations, NGOs, as well as academic and research organizations, the meeting was an excellent opportunity for networking and discussing recent trends in the community.

3.2.11 LandSense integrates Geospatial User Feedback System – Barcelona, Spain

10.05.2018

LandSense partners Secure Dimension and IIASA met with NextGEOSS and Ground Truth 2.0 experts at CREAM in Barcelona for a 2-day Hackathon to connect the Geospatial User Feedback (GUF) system, conceptually designed during the GeoViQua FP7 project, with the LandSense Engagement Platform (LEP).

This strategic addition allows us to combine automatic (LandSense QA core service) and manual (GUF) data quality to observations collected in LandSense campaigns and initiatives outside the context of LandSense, e.g. NextGEOSS, Ground Truth 2.0, and WeObserve.

3.2.12 LandSense at 3rd ECN CrowdCamp – Bologna, Italy

28.06.2018

The European Crowdfunding Network presented LandSense at its annual event CrowdCamp, in Bologna, Italy, aimed at promoting crowdfunding as an innovative finance source, educate entrepreneurs on how to use it, raise awareness among investors on its potential. Francesca Passeri discussed how to integrate crowdfunding into public budgets, as to create more leverage and improve citizens' ownership and public administrations' accountability in awarding funds to regional development projects and/or social inclusion projects. LandSense will be presented as one of the notable projects.

3.3 Common Dissemination Booster (CDB) and collaboration with other H2020 Citizen Observatories

As of the first quarter of 2018, under the umbrella of the European Commission's Common Dissemination Booster (CDB), a special relationship has been established with other H2020 citizen observatories, namely GroundTruth 2.0, GROW, and SCENT. LandSense has started collaborating with the other projects within the Common Dissemination Booster by sharing relevant EO data and information on the on-going activities within the ecosystem. This collaboration will contribute to integrating citizen science and building resilient and interconnected communities while demonstrating the societal and economic benefits of involving citizens in environmental decision making and making them “the eye” for policy makers.

Moreover, LandSense has shared the innovative ideas that spurred out of the LandSense Innovation Challenge with other H2020 Citizen Observatories, highlighting Bird's AI as a prominent and promising initiative.

4 The illustration of the value chain

The EO ecosystem as an emerging industry is seeing technical breakthroughs regarding data collection and storage and is expected to boom over the next few decades. Global players in the EO industry have recognized its opportunity to tackle large-scale and complex challenges in agriculture, climate change, biodiversity and others. As it can be seen in the figure below, the EO market can be divided into three sectors: upstream (space infrastructure), midstream (data sales) and downstream (value-adding services).

Figure 14 The Earth Observation Market

In the EO market history, EO services were predominately run by organizations financed by the space industry, with the governments being their primary financiers and their primary customers. In the upstream market, a disruptive trend emerges where private companies are investing into small and cheap satellite manufacturing, enabling the development of new markets at affordable costs (example Sentinel-2A, launched by GIM)¹. “The midstream segment sees a profusion of new and smaller actors. In 2012, only three companies captured almost three quarters of the total revenue emanating from EO commercial data sales, namely GeoEye (25%), DigitalGlobe (25%) and Astrium GEO-Information services (20%).”² Finally, the downstream market is where LandSense project is positioned. This market is considered to provide the biggest potential for both institutional and private European EO value-added information services due to their broad applicability in various industries.

¹ Recent launches of new Earth Observation satellites open up new possibilities, GIM official website, 2017. <https://www.gim.be/en/about-gim/news-events/recent-launches-of-new-earth-observation-satellites-open-up-new-possibilities>

² Digital Transformation Monitor - Big Data in Earth Observation https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/dem/monitor/sites/default/files/DTM_Big%20Data%20in%20Earth%20Observation%20v1.pdf

Stakeholder mapping includes representatives from the following different categories:

- i. policy makers and public authorities at EU level in their role as regulators of the EU Space Policy;
- ii. the European Space Agency as an implementing body of the Copernicus and Galileo programmes, but also as organisation directly representing some EU Member States;
- iii. other European agencies supporting the European Commission's space objectives, like the European Global Satellite Agency (GSA) and the Joint Research Centre (JRC) ;
- iv. other national space agencies operating satellites systems for Earth Observation;
- v. scientific experts from the academia or affiliates to think tanks; and
- vi. representatives of the business sector in the EU, including industrial federations and space clusters.

In addition, through in-situ data acquisition, the public via citizen science initiatives is also considered as a relevant stakeholder in the EO industry. Activities performed by LandSense partners are aimed at enhancing the interconnectivity and collaboration of the aforementioned stakeholders. Through this engagement with other stakeholders from the ecosystem, LandSense strengthens the value chain and ultimately enables LandSense Services to be appropriately promoted and exploited.

5 Future Activities

There some key LandSense ecosystem building activities anticipated including:

- Heidelberg University will release a publication and data product in August 2018 for EU wide gap free OSM Land use based on OSM and Sentinel 2 fusion. Also, product quality estimation and validation for products through time sync and laco-wiki.net will be conducted.
- LandSense in collaboration with the CSA project [WeObserve](#) is participating in the first Citizen Science Interoperability Experiment in September, 2018 (Stuttgart, Germany)
- LandSense anticipates a mapathon session with stakeholders from the EO-sector at the [EuroGEOSS workshop](#) in September, 2018 (Geneva, Switzerland)
- In Month 45 of the project, INOSENS will, in cooperation with LandSense partners, organize the second LandSense Innovation Challenge. The second event will be similarly structured to the first one, organized within an ongoing conference/symposium. The First LandSense Innovation Challenge finalists will be invited to participate and to contribute with their insights and presentations during the second event.

Furthermore, the LandSense Year 2 General Assembly (November, 2018) will be used to plan additional activities, which are not listed here, to boost dissemination and promote ecosystem building.

6 Conclusions

The LandSense consortium has been very active in building awareness, networking with relevant stakeholders, and organizing high-profile events to maximize impact and exploitation potential. The shared defining characteristics of all partners is the long-term and system-wide approach to engage relevant EO stakeholders and citizens in project activities, ultimately contributing to the overall EO value chain maturity and the uptake and dissemination of LandSense services. The second iteration of this D6.8 will highlight the ecosystem building events realized during the second half of the project with a key focus on the Second LandSense Innovation Challenge.

Annex

First LandSense Innovation Challenge Call

LandSense
A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

Call for Proposals LandSense Innovation Challenge

**Empowering communities to
monitor and report on their
environment**

About LandSense

[LandSense](#) is building an innovative citizen observatory to uncover the collective potential of citizen-powered science and satellite imagery to improve the way we see, map and understand the world.

The LandSense Citizen Observatory, funded by the Horizon 2020 program, will offer modern community-based environmental monitoring tools and information systems to help transform decision making. Through **Earth Observation (EO)-driven** mobile applications, LandSense promotes citizens to not only play a key role in environmental monitoring, but also to be directly involved in the co-creation of such applications. Currently within the EU's EO monitoring framework, especially in the domain of Land Use Land Cover (LULC) dynamics, there is a need for low-cost methods for acquiring high quality in-situ data to create timely, accurate and well-validated environmental monitoring products. LandSense aims to disrupt the EO data economy by creating marketable solutions that can provide a step-change in LULC monitoring activities both within and beyond Europe.

About the LandSense Innovation Challenge

The LandSense Challenge targets individuals, web-entrepreneurs, start-ups and SMEs coming from all participating Horizon 2020 countries, **to present innovative IT solutions** addressing one of the three LandSense domains: **Urban Landscape Dynamics, Agricultural Land Use, and Forest & Habitat Monitoring**. The challenge focuses on using **data streams coming from the LandSense Citizen Observatory, the Sentinel Hub Service or other relevant EO data sources** to design novel LULC solutions for a range of applications within the selected domains.

Six LandSense Challenge finalists will have the opportunity to pitch their ideas at the [Second International ECSA Conference 2018](#) on 3 June 2018 in Geneva, Switzerland.

Each of the finalists will receive:

- A travel voucher in the amount of 250 EUR per team for attending the event in Geneva
- One ticket per team at a discounted rate to attend the Second International ECSA Conference 2018 (Cost: 50 EUR)
- Business coaching and mentorship services at the challenge
- Matchmaking and networking opportunities with leading experts in EO and citizen science
- Promotional services by LandSense
- Presentation about the LandSense Engagement Platform at the Conference in Geneva

The team with the best pitch in Geneva will receive:

- A grand prize of 1,500 EUR (in the form of a check presented at the event)
- A 1 year subscription to Sentinel Hub Enterprise, worth 5,000 EUR, provided by SINERGISE
- Online business coaching and mentorship services provided by the LandSense team

Challenge Concept

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 689812

The LandSense Innovation Challenge, based on a **Hackathon concept**, supports knowledge sharing through a one-day event where participants can **present and share their technical capabilities, innovation and creativity**.

The objectives of the **LandSense Innovation Challenge** are to:

- i) **Promote the best 4 pitch presentations** that could have a **clear business impact**
- ii) **Create awareness about the LandSense project objectives and outcomes**
- iii) **Foster the community spirit within the** LandSense Citizen Observatory

About the Second International ECSA Conference 2018

The Challenge will take place during the Second International ECSA Conference 2018 in Geneva (3-5 June, 2018). This conference is aimed at scientists, practitioners, activists, funders, policy makers in the field of citizen science, non-governmental organizations, artists, and interested citizens. The main topics of the conference include discussing the role that citizens science plays to empower citizens and to increase scientific literacy, the reasons why citizens engage in citizen science, and the impacts of citizen science on social innovations, among many other related topics.

About Sentinel Hub

Sentinel Hub's trial accounts will be opened for all participants during the first stage of the challenge and will be extended for the finalists during the final Challenge. To apply for the trial account, click [here](#).

Sentinel Hub is a Copernicus Masters award winning service for cloud-based storage, processing and distribution of satellite imagery. It targets application developers and remote sensing experts to sidestep work-intensive and costly basic data processing so they can focus on creating added value services for end-users.

Sentinel Hub provides seamless and immediate access to the full worldwide archive of Copernicus Sentinel satellites (Sentinel 1, 2 and 3) as well as other sources such as Landsat 5, 7, 8, Envisat Meris and others. Services provide access to more than 2 PB of data and at this moment process more than one million requests each day, coming from users around the world, either using one of Sentinel Hub's free applications ([Sentinel Playground](#), [EO Browser](#)) or, more importantly, one of the 3rd party applications, which are powered by Sentinel Hub services. More information can be found at [Sentinel Hub](#).

How to Apply for the LandSense Challenge?

The LandSense Challenge is dedicated to facilitating the development of innovative IT applications that are addressing the field of Land Use Land Cover within one of three LandSense domains:

1. **Urban Landscape Dynamics** - This theme focuses on engaging citizens in monitoring land change in urban and peri-urban areas. Solutions should be oriented towards local decision makers to support urban monitoring and planning.
2. **Agricultural Land Use** - This theme focuses on leveraging the power of EO systems and advanced crowdsourcing techniques to deliver value-added services to European farmers and public authorities involved in the agricultural sector.
3. **Forest & Habitat Monitoring** - Solutions within these domains should support in situ data collection to help monitor protected areas such as wild life reserves, conservation areas, and other biodiversity hotspots.

The process is divided into **two stages**:

The first stage calls for ideas and invites participants to **submit proposals for IT-based LULC solutions within one of three LandSense domains**. Proposals (up to 2 pages long) should be submitted to the LandSense team by *Friday 13 April 2018 (5pm CET)*, using the following email

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 689812

address: challenge@landsense.eu. Please see the **LandSense Challenge Application Form** for further details.

The second stage includes **4 proposals** to be selected by the LandSense expert jury, where the finalists will be announced on *Friday, 27 April 2018 (5pm CET)*. *These 4 finalists will be invited to the public challenge event in Geneva. The applicants will then have over a month to finalize and further develop their solutions, demos/mock-ups, and pitch presentations to present to the jury at the LandSense Challenge.*

**If the applicants subscribe to the Sentinel Hub trial account, they are requested to inform the LandSense Team, by emailing challenge@landsense.eu the email address have they used in the registration process, so the trial account can be extended throughout first stage of the Challenge period. For finalists only will the Sentinel Hub trial account be extended after the first stage and will be open until the end of the Challenge.*

Selection Criteria

The LandSense expert jury will assess the submitted proposals based on the following selection criteria. Criteria and thresholds apply to both the first and second stage of the proposal.

Selection Criteria	Points	Thresholds
Feasibility of the concept	1-5	4
Market potential	1-5	4
Relevance for the domain	1-5	4
Total: max. 15		

Detailed description of the selection criteria

Applicants should pay attention to the following criteria when devising their idea and preparing the application.

Feasibility of the concept:

- i) Is the concept relevant to the field of Land Use and Land Cover monitoring?
- ii) Are objectives well described (specific, measurable, accepted, reasonable and time-bound)?
- iii) Is the proposed technical approach sound and appropriate for the scope of the proposal?

Market potential:

- i) Have you clearly identified the target market (size, segments, etc.)?
- ii) Do you clearly describe positioning and unique selling points?
- iii) Do you have a sound market penetration strategy?
- iv) Do you have an appropriate business and growth model in place?

Relevance for the domain:

- i) How might future environmental management and public participation impact from using your solution?
- ii) How can the new Citizens' Observatories as well as next generations of observatories re-use and tailor your solution?
- iii) How applicable is your solution for solving problems of other stakeholders relevant for the domain?

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Contact and Important Dates

For more detailed information: <https://landsense.eu/challenge>

More questions? Please contact: challenge@landsense.eu.

About Sentinel hub: <https://www.sentinel-hub.com/>

Deadline for submission of proposals: *Friday 13 April 2018, 17:00 CET*

Invitation of selected finalists until: *Friday 27 April 2018, 17:00 CET*

Challenge date in Geneva: *Sunday 3 June 2018*

First LandSense Innovation Challenge Application Form

LandSense
A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

LandSense Innovation Challenge Application Form

To submit an idea for the LandSense Challenge, you need to prepare a short description that should be sent by e-mail as a PDF file to the following address:

challenge@landsense.eu

Please use the following subject: LandSense Innovation Challenge Application

Format

Please prepare your proposal as a PDF file no longer than 2 pages plus a title page. You can optionally add 1 page with a figure, presenting your software application's architecture. Each file must not be larger than 10 MB.

Title Page

Please include the following information on the title page:

- Title of the challenge: LandSense Challenge
- Title of your proposal/idea
- Name and webpage of your organisation if applicable
- Name, email, telephone number, address of the contact person
- Date of preparation and/or version number

Content of Your Proposal

The body of your proposal should include the following parts and must not exceed 2 pages:

- Short description/abstract of your idea, clearly outlining the key elements (maximum 200 words)
- Outline the problem that you are planning to address
- Describe your envisaged solution and the key benefits/impacts
- Targeted market - foreseen customers and market size
- Roughly outline your business model
- Explain which technology you are planning to use
- Short descriptions of key personnel in the team

Use the most appropriate means to present your idea, i.e. as text, tables, graphical explanations, etc.

You may also add 1 additional page that provides a graphical overview of your envisaged software application's architecture, which will identify the main components of your solution.

Important Dates:

Submission of proposals: *Friday 13 April 2018, 17:00 CET*

Announcement of selected finalists: *Friday 27 April 2018, 17:00 CET*

Challenge in Geneva: *Sunday 3 June 2018*

First LandSense Innovation Challenge Proposal Template

Proposal for the LandSense Challenge

Title:
<Title of your proposal/idea>

Organisation Name: if applicable

Webpage: if applicable

Contact Person:
Name
Email
Telephone number
Address

**Have you used
Sentinel Hub in your
idea**

Yes

No

**If not, please specify what data
you have
used:**

Date:

Version:

Content of Your Proposal (max 2 pages)

The body of your proposal should include the following parts and must not exceed 2 pages. You are free to use text, tables or graphical explanations.

1. Relevance for the domain

The Idea (maximum 200 words)

Short description/abstract of your idea, clearly outlining the key elements.

The Problem

Outline the problem that you are planning to address

Envisaged Solution and Benefits

Explain your envisaged solution and the key benefits compared to the current situation.

Innovation

In one sentence, outline how your idea is innovative.

2. Feasibility of the concept

Business Model

Roughly outline your business model including positioning, unique selling points, and the future growth model.

Technology used

Explain the technologies you are planning to use

The Team

Briefly describe your team

3. Market potential

Market

Who is your target market, i.e. the rough size, potential customers and market penetration strategy?

Architecture of the Software Application (Optional and max 1 page)

If you consider it useful, you can add 1 additional page to add an illustration of your software/hardware architecture, which will identify the main components of your solution.

First LandSense Innovation Challenge Agenda

LandSense Challenge Agenda *Salle communale de Plainpalais, Geneva, Switzerland* 3rd of June, 2018

<p>10:00 – 10:30 Check-in at the event site and at the LandSense Challenge Room for all the challenge participants and the LandSense team 10:30 – 11:00 Challenge finalists are being introduced with the practicalities and plan for the rest of the day 11:00 – 11:15 Welcome messages & motivation by Inian Moorthy, IIASA 11:15 – 11:45 Challenge teams introducing themselves (5 minutes each) 11:45 – 12:00 Networking coffee</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teams move to their desks and get installed • Event participants will come into the room and start asking questions (What is LandSense? Why is this important for me? Where can I join?...) • LandSense people to be in the room all the time and answer participants' questions
<p>12:00 – 13:30 Bootcamp style session 12:00 – 12:30 Sentinel Hub services - Matej Batič, Sinergise 12:30 – 13:00 Pitching skills - Mladen Radišić, InoSens 13:00 – 13:30 Introduction to Citizen Science - Muki Haklay, ECSA 13:30 – 14:30 Networking lunch</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To be organized by LandSense team in the room • Anybody welcome to join in the LandSense room to attend
<p>14:30 – 16:00 Teams finalizing their applications and pitches 16:00 – 16:15 Pitch warming up break</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LandSense people to be in the room all the time and answer participants' questions • Teams busy with coding/ mockup or demo or application finalization • Jury members gathering
<p>16:15 – 17:15 Final pitches by the teams (5 minutes each + 5 minutes Q&A) 17:15 – 17:45 Final evaluation by the jury 17:45 – 18:00 Award ceremony</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anybody welcome to join in the LandSense room to watch presentations

First LandSense Challenge Survey

LandSense Challenge Feedback

Name: _____ Organization: _____

Position and Email: _____

Please rate the following information by selecting the most appropriate emoji.

1. Pre-event organization and communication was performed diligently and efficiently.
2. Have you found the speakers interesting and informing?
3. Have you found the overall organization of the LS Challenge Finals well prepared?
4. Was ESCA 2018 event setup useful for your networking opportunities?
5. Will you attend future LandSense Events and Challenges?
6. Will you further develop your idea?
7. Please leave additional comments for the LandSense Challenge organization team. What did you like the most? What would you have done differently? Any suggestions and improvements regarding future event?

Thank you for your feedback!!!!

LandSense

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